

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.4

Year 3 Report on Workshop Design Recommendations

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable reports on the stakeholder engagement with both societal and industry stakeholders undertaken as part of the consideration of social aspects of the X-ROTOR concept. It provides a summary of the feedback received from both groups, as well as recommendations for the development of the X-ROTOR concept.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

ASD	Asynchronous Structured Dialogue
DoA	Description of Action
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IET	Islay Energy Trust
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
UCC	University College Cork
UoS	University of Strathclyde
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
XRC	X-ROTOR concept

1 Introduction

An important element of the X-ROTOR project was the capture of stakeholder perspectives to feed into the design and development process. This was realized through engagement with two key stakeholder groups, namely: prospective host communities whose work and lives would be directly affected by potential deployment of such technologies; and the wider wind energy community who have a professional interest in the development of novel turbine designs such as the X-ROTOR concept.

The first group, the prospective host communities (societal stakeholders), were engaged to better understand their practices, attitudes, and values of relevance to the novel wind turbine design, and to examine how – from their perspective – the X-ROTOR design compares with conventional turbine designs.

The second group, the wider wind energy community (industry stakeholders) were engaged to ascertain their opinions and preferences on design (and related) issues including: turbine rating, siting, support structure (fixed/floating), shore-side facilities, installation requirements and operations and maintenance (O&M) practices.

1.1 Recap of Year-1 Engagements

In the first year of the project both groups had to be engaged remotely due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the associated travel and social interaction restrictions. The stakeholder workshops were therefore reimagined as asynchronous structured dialogues following the modified Delphi-panel approach after Revez *et al.*, (2020). As outlined in D7.1, this first year of engagement was intended as a soft launch, with the aim of strengthening the project long-term through fostering meaningful links and encouraging the development of a genuine relationship between the project officials and the stakeholders.

The principal finding of these workshops is that there are very different emphases from Group 1 (the host communities) and Group 2 (the wind energy community) regarding the features of a wind turbine which are considered important. Group 2 focused on the energy output while Group 1 focused on the local and environmental impact while supporting the idea of offshore energy. A secondary finding of note was that there was a great deal of similarity among Group 1 respondents across Scotland, Ireland, and Spain regarding the attitudes towards the environment and support for local jobs, and protection of fishing.

1.2 Recap of Year-2 Engagements

Group 1 was engaged through a workshop with three focus groups on the island of Islay, Scotland, which found that the local community felt vulnerable to decisions made beyond their reach. They strongly supported renewable energy but were concerned about the infrastructural needs of their small island should a large offshore wind farm be installed nearby. Regarding the X-ROTOR, they were curious & interested in the design. In summary the feedback from the societal stakeholders included:

- Small level of concern regarding visibility from shore, most did not object to seeing turbines.
- High level of concern regarding the frequency of O&M activity and consequent sea and road traffic.
- Some concern regarding the guarantee of removal and disposal of turbines after they are no longer useful for electricity generation.
- Low level of concern regarding noise as the X-ROTOR turbines would be off the coast.
- Some concern about sea bird collisions, but most participants did not express this as a concern.

Group 2 was engaged with a continuation of non-synchronous dialogue as in year 1 and through direct in-person engagements at wind energy meetings and conferences in Ireland. It is notable that this group continued to be focused on financial and reliability issues. Insights from engagement with group 2 included:

- Levelized cost of energy remained the primary concern.
- Reliability and durability of X-ROTOR in the harsh marine environment was also a concern.
- High levels of risk aversion regarding investing in a new unproven technology, while also a high level of curiosity about the X-ROTOR turbine itself.
- Low (expressed) concern about consequences for wildlife, the environment, or local communities.

2 Focus Groups

2.1 Group 1 Societal stakeholders

2.1.1 Background

In a previous report (D7.1), Deeney & Dunphy (2021a) outlined the approach and methods to be used within the project to identify and convene stakeholder communities. Over the course of the project, it is planned to involve c. 50 people (from five different host communities and at least three different

European countries and comprising at least 30% female) in these societal stakeholder engagements – this lends itself to capturing a diversity of opinion, insights from which will benefit the project.

D7.1 envisaged the recruitment and engagement of a principal host community¹, which will be the focus of the engagement. This would be supplemented by less intensive engaging of a further four satellite (or secondary) communities who will present opinions and ideas from other geographical areas, which would be recruited on a phased basis. This arrangement was decided upon as it means it is possible to focus the effort and resources of the research on a host community which is most relevant, while also listening to other communities.

It was planned that all engagement to be remote in year one (due to the pandemic) followed in subsequent years by face-to-face engagements of the principal community if circumstances permitted. The engagement of the secondary communities was to remain primarily remote for practical reasons (but perhaps supplemented by in person engagement where opportunities arose).

In the first year, stakeholders from three communities in Ireland, Spain, and the United Kingdom were engaged in an asynchronous structured dialogue. These engagements provided insights on the participants' perceptions and attitudes relevant to the design of the X-ROTOR off-shore wind turbine concept. It was evident that their principal concerns were associated with the environmental impact of offshore wind farms and with the impact on fishing. The in-depth face-to-face engagement afforded by the workshops in the second and third years coupled with the multinational online community offered a good opportunity to explore these issues in greater detail.

2.2 Group 2 Industry stakeholders

The wider wind community were also planned to be engaged remotely at first, followed by a combination of physical and online meetings coinciding with suitable conferences to facilitate participation (Deeney & Dunphy 2021a). This 'industry' community is not defined by location but rather is based upon the individuals' connection to the wind power industry, they are therefore consequently very geographically dispersed. The target engagement over the life of the project was similar in scale to group 1, with a target of c. 50 participants from at least five sectors and of which the members are at least 30% female.

The objective of this engagement with the industry stakeholders is to identify factors influencing purchasing decision for turbines in addition to Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) most commonly

¹ The principal community was intended to be one which would be likely to eventually play host to X-ROTOR technology whereas the satellite communities would be secondary choices for deployment of the technology.

cited. While D7.1 acknowledged that the face-to-face engagements would perhaps be the ideal mode, this was not possible in the first year due to the COVID related restrictions and is in any event difficult because of the wide geographical dispersal of the possible participants.

In the third year of engaging with this group we made several changes to our approach. First, we changed the survey. In the previous survey, we listed a lower LCOE as one of the attributes the importance of which we wanted participants to evaluate. Almost every respondent ranked this attribute as “very important.” It dominated the rankings. This year, we decided to remove LCOE as an attribute and just include the attributes which go into creating that lower LCOE. Thirteen of the twenty-one attributes for which we sought evaluation contribute to a lower LCOE. We were hoping to gauge which of these component parts practitioners thought most relevant to their needs. We also changed the wording of some attribute descriptions and included a few new ones. Table 1 below is a comparison of the different attribute descriptions.

Table 1: Comparison of attribute descriptions between years 1 & 2 and year 3

Attribute Descriptions Used in Years 1 and 2 Surveys (order of list changed to highlight comparison with updated survey. Note: some attributes are only tangentially related, some not at all)	Attribute Descriptions Used in Year 3 Survey
Purchase cost	Lower material cost
Visibility	Limited view-scape intrusion
Installation cost	Reduced installation cost
Likelihood of collision with birds	Designed to reduce bird collisions
Maintenance cost	Lower maintenance requirements/increased ease
Levelized cost of electricity	Capacity factor above 60%
Effect on wildlife	Reduced impact on marine life
Choice of power capacity	Nameplate rating above 10 MW
Impact on fishing industry	Placement that reduces conflicts with shipping and fishing activities
Choice of fixed or floating	Capable of placement in waters 60 m – 1,000 m deep
Impact on shipping	Single day installation
Ability to survive extreme conditions	Survivability
Onshore requirements	Community acceptability
Noise output	Noise output
Impact on scenery	Foundations capable of artificial reef creation
Effect on local people	Local job creation
Choice of height	Possibility of quay-side construction and staging
Effect on radio and radar signals	Gearless direct drive
O&M cost	Does not require jack-up boat
Not mentioned in years 1 or 2	Reduced wind turbine wakes and Possibility of government subsidies/ FiT/RESS

The second thing we did differently was to abandon the efforts of trying to gather focus groups of industry representatives (Group 2) and just concentrate on one-on-one interviews that we conducted at various trade shows, exhibitions, and conferences. Though a focus group would have provided information on how the industry professionals interact with each other over the discussion topics, getting them in a room together all at the same time and place proved to be logistically prohibitive. We had great success at the WindEurope Exhibition in Copenhagen (2023) speaking with many different wind energy professionals and learned much from these interactions which will be described in Section 4 below. As a result, we decided to repeat this approach in our following Group 2 engagements.

3 Engagements and Results - Societal Stakeholders

3.1 Overview

3.1.1 Focus group as a research tool

An in-person engagement event with three focus groups was held for what might be considered a possible partner community to that of Islay which we designated as the primary host community last year. This community is located in Malin Head, Ireland, which is just across the water from Islay. These two communities are separated by about 40 nautical miles of the ocean where X-ROTOR might be deployed at some point in the future. As such, the machines could conceivably be half-way between them, and it is therefore possible that both communities could support the work and benefit from the deployment. The workshop was organized and realized by a team with members from both University College Cork (UCC) and the University of Strathclyde (UoS).

In the first year of X-ROTOR a survey tool was used with the group 1 participants. Surveys are great tools for getting at what people may think or feel about a certain topic, but some things may be too new or novel for most people to have formed an opinion about them. This is where a focus group can be useful. These small, safe settings allow people to explore different perspectives on an issue and do a better job of revealing detailed information and providing thoughtful insight (Gibbs, 1997).

For participants to feel comfortable and for the researcher to explore some issues in depth, these groups work best if the participants are of a relatively homogenous group and if the questions are few in number (Morgan, 1996). As regards the participants, this should be a group of at least five people and no more than ten (Masadeh, 2012). This will allow for some diversity of opinion while also allowing for each person ample time and space to express themselves. The homogeneity of the group is important because it allows the researcher to focus on how a planned programme, policy, or project

will affect a specific demographic or subset of the population. It also allows for the participants to feel a comfort level in the shared experiences of their fellow participants (Freeman, 2006). It will usually take more than one focus group for the results to be valid, most often three or four (Masadeh, 2012).

3.1.2 Organisation

The X-ROTOR engagement event was scheduled to occupy the first two hours of a day-long event titled *The Wind and Wave Energy Day*. Peter Deeney, one of the X-ROTOR researchers, has extensive connections to Malin Head having lived and worked there for 12 years. In fact, he was part of the committee which contracted to have the community building renovated where we were holding the event.

The event's function was to inform the community of three different renewable energy options appropriate

Figure 1: Malin Head Event Focus Group Facilitators: L-R, Luke Smith, Dorcas Mikindani, Peter Deeney, Nicola Baxter (University of Strathclyde), and Kevin Campbell

for their area and to gather feedback on what they thought, the X-ROTOR concept, wave energy, and community land-based wind energy.

3.1.3 Recruitment

We placed an advertisement in the *Inishowen Independent* and the event's happening was picked up from there and reported about in the *Inish Times*. It was also reported in an online newspaper – *The Donegal Daily*. A further piece about the event was broadcast on *Highland Radio*, the radio station with the greatest listenership on the whole peninsula. Incidentally, that is how the two offshore wind energy developers heard about the event. In addition, a communication campaign was implemented targeting community organizations on Malin Head with customised email requests for their participation. Organizations contacted included those representing fishers, crabbers, senior citizens, the disabled, environmentalists, people of faith, economic developers, etc. These outreach activities directed people to the project website's registration page for the focus group. This explained the purpose of the focus group and allowed people to register online.

Sixteen participants were recruited for the workshop which enabled three sub-groups to be formed, with a member of the UCC/UoS research team serving as a facilitator in each one. The element of homogeneity pulling everyone together is that they were all members of the small coastal community

of Malin Head (the two ocean energy developers were from further afield) and they each had an interest in learning about new renewable energy ideas that might work for their community.

3.1.4 Meeting structure and discussion prompts

The discussions were introduced briefly and guided by the team members present. Sound recordings were made, which subsequently informed this report.

Nicola Baxter presented the X-ROTOR concept which she had refined based upon feedback from the previous year's presentation in Islay. She discussed the background of the project, the engineering team, the concept itself in more detail, its advantages over traditional offshore wind turbines, and its future plans.

After the presentation, we broke up into three focus groups to learn what our participants thought of the idea. Focus Group A, led by Ms Baxter, contained an offshore wind energy developer for a new start-up company, two hydrogen fuel cell researchers, a surfer, a finance graduate student, and a staffer for the Donegal County Council member representing Inishowen (Malin Head's district). Group B, led by Dr Deeney, contained a professional fisherman, an aquaculturist, a geo-systems student, an oil and gas engineer, and another engineer. Group C, led by Dr Smith, was composed of a community development specialist, a retiree interested in wave energy, a prosumer (solar PV) and former STEM professional, a community relations specialist with a small offshore wind energy company, and a PhD student from Tanzania.

Though we did have a list of discussion prompts should people be shy, it turns out that none of the groups needed them as they had plenty of questions and opinions of their own. The results of these discussions are presented in section 4.1 below.

3.2 Findings from the Malin Head engagement event

In the first year of the X-ROTOR project Malin Head (County Donegal, Ireland) residents were contacted and asked to reply to a survey that researchers were using to establish a baseline on their attitudes toward climate change and offshore wind energy. For the reader's convenience, Figure 3 below contains the overall results of that survey that were initially reported in D7.2.

Figure 2: Slide from the X-ROTOR design presentation

Figure 3: Group 1 Agreement Scores for Topics (Deeney & Dunphy, 2021b, p. 11)

The meeting with the community began with Dr Deeney communicating these results to the audience gathered, some of whom had taken the survey two years previous. The UCC research team felt this was important to help reinforce the levels of trust we have with this community. Unfortunately, the only reason and occasion most scientists communicate their findings with the public is when they feel it necessary to defend their work against misinformation (Dudo and Besley, 2016). As the UCC team relies upon engaging with the public, we are keenly aware of how important it is to establish and maintain trust with the public. Our motivation is to prevent reactions like this one quoted below from a participant in a public engagement campaign and reported upon in an article about participatory research:

In the past we have seen many other organizations and people coming here. They would use the information they got from this area and do whatever they were gonna do with it and we never got back the results from whatever they were doing. Some of it may have been mistrust (Belone et al., 2016, p. 123).

Dr Deeney reported the results of his previous work with the community, and we will make this report available to them once it is published.

This report on our findings from the focus groups convened in Malin Head, Ireland, on the 15th of June, 2023, will follow a two-pronged approach. First, topics discussed in each of the groups (or at least two out of three) will be discussed under the heading of “Common Topics” and then topics which were only raised in individual focus groups will be discussed under the heading of “Individual Topics.”

Figure 4: Dr Deeney presents findings from the 2021 engagement

3.2.1 Common topics

There were five topics about which participants had either questions or comments that seemed to crop up in each group – technical aspects, the electricity system in general, the proposed location of the turbines, the environmental impacts, and the local economic impacts.

Technical aspects. Each of the focus groups had at least one engineer as well as others with a scientific background. There were a few questions about the secondary rotors mainly focusing on whether they were high enough over sea level and how powerful they were. In answer to the first, we can say that the highest significant wave height as measured by a buoy and recorded by the World Meteorological Organization was 19 meters in the waters between Iceland and the UK (2023).² As the secondary rotors are 25 – 30 meters above sea-level, they are probably high enough to avoid collision with waves. In relation to their power out-put we were able to say at the time that each turbine will be rated at around 2.5MW.

Other technical questions focused on whether the turbines could be used to electrolyze water to produce hydrogen, what was the manner of power transfer between and through the two rotating axes points to the transmission line, and what were the physical dimensions of the device overall. We were able to provide responses to these queries and were even able to use the second one about power transfer to highlight a technical innovation developed by our researchers. This innovation has to deal with the wireless transfer of large amounts of power over a small airgap of 5mm (Yazdanpanah, *et al.*, 2022). To the best of our knowledge, this feat has never been done.

There were technical questions to which we did not have an answer and said they were still under discussion. One of these was about the material from which the turbines would be constructed. Another was about whether the devices were scalable to larger power out-puts, and a last was about what exactly were the cut-in and cut-out wind speeds.

One participant was skeptical about all aspects of the X-ROTOR that were presented. This person held that theoretical or analytical “knowledge” about the device was unfounded and that the only thing that mattered was building it and testing its performance then.

The electricity system. There was greater-than-expected interest in how the electricity system on the peninsula would have to change if there was any sizeable development of offshore wind energy in the waters off Malin Head. Many participants welcomed the prospect of an upgraded grid noting that

² Buoy K5 (a part of the UK Met Office’s network of Marine Automatic Weather Stations, or MAWS)[59°07.3’N, 11°42.5’W] (*Ibid.*).

the present one was unreliable and did not have the capacity to support the electricity usage that would be needed to welcome larger industries or even accommodate a transition to heat pumps and electric vehicles.

Regarding grid upgrades, there was concern that there would not really be any upgrades to the local grid, only to the high voltage (HV) transmission system. Not only would grid improvements pass them by, but there would likely be new HV lines and towers polluting the scenic atmosphere of their village. There was some discussion that these changes may be permissible if the community was going to benefit, specifically through better service and lower electricity prices.

Location. There was seeming unanimous agreement that the turbines, no matter whether they were traditional horizontal axis machines or x-rotors,³ needed to be out of sight. This opinion was different than it was in Islay where concern over visual impacts were much less vehement. In fact, in Islay there was even some support for having the turbines within the viewscape as a testament to the forward-thinking disposition of the community. Though some participants wished for the turbines to be closer to the Islay side, there was no discussion on how this would affect any potential partnership between the two communities.

Other considerations about location focused on the X-ROTOR design. People like that it was suited to a floating foundation as the continental shelf drops off quickly, though there was some concern that Malin Head's large waves may pose some issues. The possibility of having more turbines in a smaller area without losing any power production appealed to those concerned with conflict-of-use issues around fishing and shipping.

Environmental Concerns. In two of the three focus groups, there did not appear to be much concerned about the possible negative environmental impacts of the X-ROTOR concept (divergent perspectives described in 4.1.2). People did not think it expressed a danger to birds and even thought that since it was believed to be a loud machine this would help further deter any wildlife interactions. A member of Focus Group C did have concerns that the increased volume would impact sea mammals and wanted to make sure that this was tested for before any of the units were deployed. Some people even expressed the idea that the structures could serve as artificial reefs and even help improve the fish stocks for Malin Head fishers.

³ All in lower case because it is referring to the device itself instead of the project or concept. In the latter use, X-ROTOR is actually an acronym standing for X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction.

Local Economic Impacts. Almost everyone thought that X-ROTOR offered the potential to benefit the local economy. The rural economic development specialist put it succinctly when she said that [paraphrased] it was important that we look at this opportunity through the lens of contributing to a circular economy and one that prioritizes the local provision of goods and services. Following this idea, a few people asked what aspects of the supply chain could be met by local producers and if there was a way that the development could contribute to an upgraded grid that would entice larger manufacturers to the area to fabricate the steel and electrical components.

There was more interest in some form of partial ownership of the farm, but there was no agreement on what would comprise a just number of turbines and whether they should be gifted or purchased at cost. Many people thought that this form of community compensation was better than the industry standard of a community benefit fund (CBF). Even if there was a potential that a CBF at €2/MWh could be more lucrative, as long as the community-owned turbines supplied enough power on balance for the whole community they felt like that would instill a greater sense of pride and make them more like a part of the transition to a sustainable energy future. Surprisingly, one of the offshore wind energy developers agreed and thought that companies would rather have partners than passive beneficiaries even if in the end it meant that they would garner slightly less profits.⁴

3.2.2 Individual Topics

In this section we discuss topics that arose in each of the focus groups but were not raised in the other two. Though these opinions may be considered minority views, they often represent concerns of an entire subset who may be more affected by ocean energy development than the average citizen. The concerns of a surfer in Focus Group A is a good example.

Focus Group A.

The surfer in Focus Group A (FGA) expressed particular concern about the effects of marine renewable energy development on the quality of the surf. Though surfers self-identify as environmentalists at much higher rates than the average non-surfer (Hill & Abbott, 2009; Wheaton, 2007), they also tend to develop a stronger attachment to the places they surf than do other ocean recreationalists of the same area (Larson, *et al.*, 2018). It is this place attachment which we theorize

⁴ One participant did note to his group, one that did not contain one of the developers, that the company's profits would not be affected as they would just adjust their tariff bid accordingly. He felt that the government's emission goals would require the purchase of offshore wind even if it was a euro or two more per MWh. This same person also asked what difference to him does it matter if the capital and O&M costs are lower for X-ROTOR, it is not like the savings will be passed on to him (assuming the community does not purchase a turbine or two at cost but rather just collects the €2/MWh).

may be at the root of not only this individual's initial reaction against marine renewable energy development in his area, but it may be at the base of many negative reactions to renewable energy development among people who otherwise claim to be environmentally orientated. What is often derogatorily referred to as NIMBYism (not-in-my-back-yard-ism) attitudes on the part of objectors may in fact be a natural reaction to protecting a place that holds a special value in the objector's mind.

A theory which has gained some ground in offering a more workable approach to understanding this objection rather than NIMBYism is the social representations theory (SRT). The scholar most closely associated with this idea is Serge Moscovici (*e.g.*, see 2001), though many others have written on it. Basically, the use of this approach is that it grounds opposition to new renewable energy projects not in a derogatory rendition of peoples' motives, but as a natural product of the way people incorporate change. Under this theory, people do not accept change simply by replacing one idea with another, newer one. On the contrary, people hold both ideas at the same time even if they are contradictory. What SRT proposes is that people come to accept the new idea through a process of making the unfamiliar familiar. This is accomplished through a process of how they represent their reality not only to themselves, but maybe even more fundamentally in how they represent their reality to each other (Moscovici, 2001).

The facilitator's objective in dialoguing with this individual was to determine what representations he had of the area and then discover whether development of the X-ROTOR could be consistent with and non-detrimental to those representations. It turns out that the surfer was most concerned with how the turbine(s) might affect the quality of the waves for surfing. The facilitator was able to provide a representation of the surf that was unimpacted from X-ROTOR and possibly even improved. On the first, the machines would likely be far enough from shore that the diminished upper-level wake would have recovered in plenty enough time to maintain the effect it was having on the ocean waves before they encountered the turbine [a conclusion drawn from reading sources like (Sun, *et al.*, 2019)]. Secondly, there is even some evidence that offshore wind turbines increase the wind velocity close to the water's surface and may therefore improve the quality of the surf (Wimer, 2014). Introducing ideas like these helped the surfer to see that X-ROTOR development was not a threat to his valued surfing spot. Situations where there may be an impact on the associations a person has in regard to the area take more work to incorporate dissimilar representations. For example, if turbines have to be placed in the viewscape, the developer needs to make efforts to involve the community in the project somehow, for example, like through providing ownership opportunities or creating an amenity like raised walking trails amongst the bog-placed turbines, or other creative options (Vuichard, *et al.*, 2022; Wind Energy Ireland, 2023; Kelman, *et al.*, 2017).

Focus Group B

In Focus Group B there were both a professional fisherman and an aquaculturist. Though fishing only occupies a small portion of the Irish GDP – roughly 0.27% [$€1.3 \text{ B} / €482.31 \text{ B} * 100$ (*The Fishing Daily*, 2023; *Trading Economics*, 2023) – it has a long tradition in many coastal towns and is fundamental to their place-based identity (Donkersloot, 2010) As such, representatives of this industry have a strong voice in offshore renewable energy planning (Gusatu, *et al.*, 2020). These participants in Group B politely expressed their scepticism that any offshore wind energy project would not negatively impact their livelihood.

The facilitator, drawing on a knowledge of social representations theory, was able to draw out from them a concrete description of their concerns and then parlay that concern into the manifestation of an opportunity for them to influence the planning of any offshore development (Jentoft & Knol, 2014). Their practical concerns focused on the effect of the electromagnetic field surrounding the HVDC cables on bottom dwelling species like crabs and lobsters and on the reduction of fishing grounds due to the OWP installation. In both cases, the facilitator created a space for them to think about how these issues could be resolved and let them develop the solutions themselves.

As to the cables, the solution was to make sure they were buried deep enough, and for the reduction in the fishing area, they were able to ascertain that the X-ROTOR needed less space between turbines and so the intrusion on their fishing grounds from these devices would be less severe than with traditional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs).⁵ Though both these suggestions can make a substantive contribution to the future planning of any wind farm, the real benefit here, and for these participants in particular, is that it helped empower them to influence their own surroundings. One of these gentlemen said that fishers feel powerless and that they expect the government to push through offshore wind power despite their concerns. The facilitator thanked them for the observations and pointed out that by contributing to this dialogue they were creating documentation of both the issue and possible solutions for engineers to consult as they plan this development in the future. By speaking up here today, they would have influence on the planners' decision processes.

⁵ Unfortunately, this perceived benefit may not actually materialize. Because traditional HAWTs require so much space between them, it may be easier to allow fishing between them. Whereas with X-ROTOR, it is still undetermined whether the space between installations would allow for fishing. It is true, however, that a farm of x-rotors would be smaller overall than a farm of HAWTs of the same power rating. But for a complication, consider a farm of HAWTs that have three times the nameplate rating of the proposed X-ROTOR devices.

Focus Group C

Though all groups did have questions and or comments about the local economic impacts of X-ROTOR, the discussion in Group C was more detailed and occupied a greater portion of the conversation. The discussion focused on how to incorporate a potential X-ROTOR development within a circular economy that maximized the creation of a local supply chain for a farm of the devices. It was thought that the supply chain could not really develop until the local grid was upgraded and that would not happen, if even at all, until at least a few turbines had already been built and were operation. The issue then would be how to get the manufacturing to switch from wherever it was occurring at the beginning of the project to local suppliers. The conclusion tentatively reached is that a local manufacturing base would have to be subsidized at some level before construction even began. A separate discussion ensued regarding the pros of overbuilding the farm.

If the farm were built to a capacity greater than what a local grid could accept, could not extra income be derived from connecting to a North Atlantic transmission hub or to dropping lines directly to Spain and France? As may be perceived, these talks were far-thinking and extremely hypothetical. Another point was raised that extra power production could be used to produce green hydrogen which could be a valuable commodity in its own right. Locally, the hydrogen could be combined with the biofuel produced from anaerobic digesters on the area's dairy farms to make methanol which is easy to transport and could have uses in sustainable airplane fuel.

Related, the prosumer wondered if there were low-cost, household scale fuel cells on the horizon that consumers could purchase to power their homes on the hydrogen produced. He further theorized that if such uses were diffused nationwide it could change how we think about future grid development and the necessity for an international network of HVDC transmission lines which, perhaps in reference to recent acts by Russia on Ukraine's infrastructure, could be attacked by nefarious actors. Bringing this talk back to local economics, the rural development specialist wondered if hydrogen could be used in an eco-friendly steel manufacturing process the product of which would go back into building more turbines. Focus Group C was full of futurists, or, more charitably, people trying to visualize a pathway to a just and carbon-free world. Rather than condemn conversations such as this fanciful and unproductive, the facilitator encouraged this discourse as a way to leave the participants with a positive perspective of their country's future and a belief in the ability of their community to contribute to that state of affairs.

3.3 Findings from the online engagement

Participants from Spain (north and east coasts), France (northwest and south coasts), Portugal, and Norway took part in the final host community engagement. Some of these participants also had personal experience of coastal life in USA, Ireland, Mexico, and Denmark. The group was evenly divided 5 men and 5 women. The range of locations indicates the success of the strategy of conducting this engagement as a series of online interviews. The use of interviews allowed each participant to share their ideas and opinions at their own pace and in their own words. This approach complemented the focus group method used in Scotland and Ireland. The use of interviews also addressed the difficulty encountered when we tried to attract a sufficient number of English-speaking participants from a single non-English-speaking European country (reflecting the linguistic limitations of the researchers), as had been the original plan. Following from the reporting of Section 4.1 above, common and individual topics have been extracted from the discussions with the participants.

Table 2: Summary of topics of interest raised by participants during interviews about offshore wind.

			A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Environment	Fish	5		*		*	*			*	*	
	Crabs, Lobsters	2				*					*	
	Dolphins	2		*		*						
	Birds	4			*			*		*		*
	Water quality	3				*	*			*		
	Decommissioning	4			*	*		*		*		
	Better than others	3			*	*		*				
Leisure	Swimming	3	*					*	*			
	Sailing	4	*					*	*	*		
	Surfing	3	*					*	*			
	Fishing	4	*					*	*			*
Commercial	Fishing	7		*			*	*	*	*	*	*
	Cargo Ships	3						*		*	*	
	Cruise Ships	2						*		*		
	Tourism	3		*			*	*				
Aesthetic	Sea Views	7		*	*	*	*			*	*	*
	Noise	6			*	*	*		*	*		*
	Spiritual	2	*								*	

3.3.1 Common topics

Marine environment, with subtopics: fish, crabs, shrimp and lobsters, dolphins and other marine mammals, birds, water quality, decommissioning and consideration of the alternatives if wind isn't used.

Concern was expressed widely about the effects of offshore wind turbines on the marine environment and wildlife. The most common issue was the effect on fish from the noise coming from the turbines during installation and operation. There has not yet been research conducted on the noise effects of the X-ROTOR on fish. This may be a useful direction for future projects looking at the noise, particularly noise during the operation of the turbines since the vibrations from X-ROTOR are likely to be different from those of HAWTs. Concerns were also expressed regarding what may be done with the turbines after they are no longer in use. This split into concerns about decommissioning of blades and issues about the life cycle of the turbines. Several participants knew that wind turbine blades were difficult to recycle as they are made from fiberglass. Questions were asked about the overall energy consumed in extraction and manufacture of the turbines compared to the energy extracted from the wind. Questions were also asked about the life cycle carbon dioxide emissions. This showed a high degree of sophistication and knowledge on behalf of the participants, but a lack of detail. Some of this was inspired by the difficulty of decommissioning nuclear power plants, where it seemed that plans for the end of life were not robust enough to be successful. It may be useful to examine whether the lower turbine location of the X-ROTOR design makes decommissioning easier than HAWTs. It would be useful to disseminate the results with interested parties.

Participants were aware of the presence of many types of animals in the sea and were particularly concerned about birds and dolphins both of which had been seen by participants quite frequently. As well as concern for the environment, participants were aware that offshore wind of any sort would be less impactful on the environment than alternative sources of energy such as nuclear, coal or gas power stations. In particular, some of the participants acknowledged that bits of broken turbines washing up on the beach were much less trouble than an oil slick.

Leisure use of the sea is an important common topic, sub themes were swimming, sailing, surfing, and fishing.

The sea is used widely for leisure pursuits such as swimming, sailing, surfing, and swimming. All of these were mentioned more or less equally by participants. Concern was expressed about the need to share the available space so that people using the sea would be safe, especially people who go out in

boats who may not have the level of professional training or navigational equipment and skill to avoid turbines in bad visibility. It would seem reasonable to point out that X-ROTOR turbines can be packed more closely together, and this may help to address some of these concerns.

Commercial uses of the sea, had subtopics of fishing, cargo ships, cruise ships and tourism.

Commercial users of the sea were mentioned widely, and the most common are of concern was for fishing. It was clear that many of the participants were aware of the conflict of interest between offshore wind and the fishing industry, and its allied industries in food preparation. These provide important jobs in remote locations. Concern was also expressed for cargo ships, tourism and to a lesser extent cruise ships. Like leisure users of the sea, it would seem that clear delineation of areas of use would address these concerns.

The tourism industry was mentioned widely as supporting remote coastal communities, and that offshore wind farms may be damaging to the image of tranquillity and peace which such areas wish to use to support their tourism businesses. This is a concern which is partly addressed by the shorter height and tighter packing of X-Rotors, and the possibility that tourists may actually want to see turbines. There is at present a wind farm near Copenhagen which offers tourists the chance to visit⁶.

Aesthetic uses of the sea, had subtopics of scenery, noise and spiritual connection.

A more diverse aspect of the opinions and concerns expressed are the use of the sea as an inspiration or source of beauty. There were concerns about the change that turbines would make to the seascape. This may be rooted in an aversion to change for those who have been looking at the sea for many years before wind turbines have been installed offshore. At the same time one of the participants said explicitly that she found offshore wind turbines in Denmark to be “pretty”. X-ROTORs are of course slightly shorter (and wider) than HAWTS, and so this may be able to address at least some of this concern.

There was concern that noise from turbines offshore would be damaging to people’s mental health, much as listening to noise from onshore turbines has been found to be disturbing. This is of course a subject for more research, but the more tightly packed possibilities for X-ROTOR and their ability to be used farther off the coast on floating platforms may address these concerns.

⁶ Middelgrunden Wind Farm <https://ribalex.dk/webshop/product/offshore-windmill-climbing-en/?lang=en> Accessed 26th April 2024.

3.3.2 *Individual topics*

These were concerns which were raised by only one participant, they cover a wide range of interests.

Since the blades of the turbines are deliberately placed nearer the sea surface, there would seem to be a risk of collision, especially when there is a large swell. While this may not be a significant threat for professionally piloted vessels, it may be a problem for tall leisure craft such as sailing yachts. This problem would seem to be specific to X-ROTOR.

The experience of what the sea means for different people is in part a reflection of the social divisions in wider society. Thus, there may be opposition or support for offshore wind energy based on social pressure rather than on the actual effects of being near the turbines. Whether this would be different for X-ROTOR and HAWTs is an interesting question.

There is an inevitable tension between environmental and economic concerns for offshore energy projects, as for many kinds of industrial development. X-ROTOR is in the position of being slightly shorter and more densely packed than HAWTs, and so may be preferred in this balance between the environment and the economy.

While it may be expected that more financially well-off people would be more supportive of environmental concerns, this is not clear. In one of the participant's opinions local owners of larger beach front houses were more concerned about their view of the seascape being disturbed, than about the progress of renewable energy. Also, the local financially worse off people were hoping for job opportunities from offshore wind projects. These tensions are also present between newcomers to an area who may buy property in an undeveloped scenic area, and established populations who may be glad to welcome investment and a new local industry.

One of the participants was particularly concerned with the level of support shown by the government for nuclear power. In addition to the support there was a feeling that so much money had been sunk into nuclear power, that the uptake of renewable energy was less than it might otherwise have been. This lack of investment in renewables would be more likely to affect a new technology like X-ROTOR than established HAWTs.

A participant felt that increased visibility of blades may enable birds to avoid them. It would be interesting to examine if the higher rotational speed of the X-ROTOR turbines, their sound and smaller size would be less dangerous for birds.

One participant raised the issue of community benefit for those living beside offshore wind farms. Since the local community will have at least some impact from the construction traffic, maintenance operations, interruptions to local port activities and change of visual amenity, there is a need to address these impacts with some local benefits. These benefits may include financial support for the local community, improvements for the infrastructure and arranging substations so that the local community would have access to the energy produced offshore. This last idea is particularly important for remote communities which may have frequent power outages due to their location.

4 Engagement and Results – Industry Stakeholders

4.1 Background

In the second year of this process, after COVID necessitated asynchronous dialogues in the first, it was envisioned that we would be able to convene focus groups of industry stakeholders and have a number of them in a room so that our research could benefit from the give and take between participants as well as from their individual contributions. Unfortunately, this approach proved logistically untenable. The busy schedules of this stakeholder group and their geographical low density made it impossible to get a number of these individuals in a room together for a few hours. So, following wisdom of old, we decided that if they cannot come to us, we need to go to them.⁷

In this new phase, we sent researchers to canvass industry exhibitions, tradeshow, and conferences to circulate and talk with delegates, presenters, and vendors in on-on-one brief interviews. The researchers would introduce the X-ROTOR concept, talk to industry representative about it to gather their impressions, and ask the individual to complete the survey (results discussed in section 6 on attribute matching). Sometimes, the interviewee would rather talk than fill out the survey, which does align with our intent. In fact, these discussions provided more nuanced information that the survey cannot really capture. Other times, the individual would complete the survey but not be able to spare time outside that activity to speak much with the interviewer. This was acceptable too as it allowed us to collect more information on the attribute matching task of the project. Altogether, a win-win.

⁷ The saying referenced first appeared in print in an essay, “Of Boldness” by Francis Bacon (1561 – 1626): “*Mahomet called the hill to him again and again; but when the hill flood still, he, nothirly abafied, fays `if the hill will not come to Mahomet, Mahomet will go to the hill`”* (1787, p. 57).

This method of engaging with industry professional proved more fruitful than we originally anticipated.

4.2 Findings from WindEurope Exhibition interviews in Copenhagen, Denmark

The WindEurope Exhibition in Copenhagen this year (2023) presented a great opportunity to meet and speak with professionals in the wind energy industry. There were 15,800 attendees and over 500 exhibits (Wind Europe, 2023). The researchers did not attend any of the numerous speaking engagements, but rather spent their time speaking with exhibitors and the attendees who were milling about any one of the four exhibition halls between events. Researchers spoke with approximately 45 individuals from 40 different

Figure 5: Photo of exhibition floor from c. 2020 (Wind Europe, 2023)

firms/companies/organizations (listed in Appendix 2). The figure above displays approximately one-quarter of one exhibition hall. The paragraphs which follow describe some of the interesting information we gathered from speaking with the Group 2 stakeholders at this event.

LCOE. Lowering the levelized cost of energy seemed to be the most predominant concern of Group 2 members. This was stated as the only concern by at least six of the interviewees. This finding is consistent with that of years one and two. It is also why we changed the survey. With the new survey we are interested in finding out which components of the LCOE this group thinks are the most important. Is it material costs, installation costs, balance of systems costs, operation and maintenance costs, discount rate, decommissioning costs, power production, survivability, *etc.*

Load on the vertical axis bearing. There were two consultants (one from a firm and another associated with an academic institution) who were concerned with the loads which would be placed on the bearing at the top of the shaft of the vertical axis. They were concerned with the sinusoidal behaviour of the secondary rotors in combination with the rotation of the primary blades and the oceanic forces of the wind and waves. They just thought it would be a lot to handle and try to model. This same concern was expressed by an engineer at the Islay engagement event.

The secondary rotors. Three interviewees had comments about the smaller horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs). One magazine publisher commented that the University of Ghent has a program specializing in these smaller types of wind turbines. Two other individuals had suggestions about

performing maintenance on these turbines as they are placed rather precariously 30 meters above the ocean with no visible surface from which maintenance workers could perch to complete their tasks. One marine vessel operator mentioned that a Buckley crane stabilizer could be employed because its gyroscoped construction provides a stable platform on the ocean by compensating in real time for three different ranges of motion. Another interviewee who trains offshore wind turbine technicians said that much maintenance these days is done with rope work. He said that we should be sure to build in eyelets on the main shaft of the downward blade so that technicians could run ropes through them to support themselves. If removing the entire nacelle was an option, that could also be done with ropes assuming that it did not weigh more than 500 kg.

Resonance issues. A representative from a Spanish renewable energy developer and operator, said upon learning that the current X-ROTOR concept was designed for a jacket foundation that he believed this might cause resonance issues. What this individual was just guessing at was raised as a possible problem at the previous consortium meeting in September of 2022 in Barcelona. He said that he thought a floating foundation would serve the turbine better in this regard.

Survivability. After cost, survivability was topmost on the list of concerns from these Group 2 participants. Four interviewees brought up at the start of the conversation that the lifespan and survivability of the device was of utmost importance to them. A blade manufacturer was concerned with whether we had anticipated the corrosiveness of the environment on the structure and its many moving parts. A representative from a weather service provider thought the device may be able to work in many different types of environments but had his doubts about whether the North Atlantic would be one of these. Full disclosure, this comment came after he had asked where it was to be installed and the researcher had suggested in the North Atlantic between the Inner Hebrides of Scotland and the northern tip of Ireland. He mentioned that his company specialized in predicting the performance and survivability of offshore wind turbine designs using accurate metocean data over long historical periods.

Gearless drive. Surprisingly, only one interviewee mentioned the gearless drive feature of the X-ROTOR design. This is surprising because gearbox failures can cause long downtimes and consequently high O&M costs (Bhardwaj, *et al.*, 2019; Jenkins, *et al.*, 2022). A representative from a wind energy developer and operator also said that a gearless drive only has an advantage if the device is far from shore. The assumption here is that gearless drives are only necessary if transmitting direct current. Lack of comment on this feature seems odd since the trend in large offshore wind

turbines is to use gearless direct drives (Bensalah, *et al.*, 2022; Sartori, *et al.*, 2018; McDonald & Bhuiyan, 2017).⁸

Birds. At the exhibition, researchers spoke with representatives from two organizations that conducted bird monitoring around wind turbine facilities. Neither one thought that the X-ROTOR presented a unique threat to birds, but for different reasons. One interviewee thought that the loud noise of the secondary turbines would ward them off. Another disagreed with that analysis. He said that the reason birds would avoid the secondary rotors was because they were small enough that the bird would be able to see the area of the danger. He said that is the real problem with large HAWTs. The swept area is so large that the bird does not see it as a distinct threat. Either way, there are reasons to think that avian mortality would be less with X-ROTOR than with traditional offshore wind turbines.

Certification. Researchers spoke with representatives from two different certification organizations to find out what might be involved in certifying the X-ROTOR at a technology readiness level (TRL) of 9, proven and commercially viable. A representative of one company said that a new wind turbine design could conceivably move from a TRL of zero to nine in only two-and-a-half to three years. This was good news as the researcher was working on the assumption that this achievement would not be reached for another 6 years at a minimum. Two-and-a-half is surely optimistic, but it is encouraging that the possibility exists. A representative from another certification organization, surprised the researcher as the only interviewee to comment that community acceptability was the most important criterium to consider in any new turbine design. She said simply that if the device was unacceptable for the neighboring community, it would not be installed. Period. It was refreshing to hear such candor from a certifying service provider.

Figure 6: One day installation unlikely with traditional offshore wind turbines. Photo of model at the exhibition with Heerema crane vessel

One-day installation. A consultant and an offshore wind energy developer were both impressed with the prospect that the X-ROTOR devices could be constructed quayside and towed out to their operating location and installed in one day, maybe not even a whole day would be required. The

⁸ "It can be concluded that due to the elimination of the gearbox, the direct-drive systems offer better performances compared to geared ones, including low maintenance cost, higher reliability, reduced noise and higher efficiency" (Bensalah, *et al.*, 2022, p. 29).

consultant was impressed with this fact in that it would enable a greater possibility of local employment and supply chain provisioning. The wind energy developer representative was attracted to the prospect that the short window needed for installation would enable quicker farm formation and lower costs for the installation team and transport.

4.3 Findings from WESC interviews in Glasgow, Scotland

The University of Strathclyde hosted this year's WESC event at their Technology and Innovation Centre in the heart of downtown Glasgow. It was an action packed four days from the 23rd of May to the 26th attended by well over 1,000 participants from academia and industry. There were hundreds of presentations over the four days, eight of them by members of the X-ROTOR team in two separate mini-symposiums. This was the fourth WESC event since its inauguration in 2017 and gathered together leading scientists and researchers in the field of wind energy.

Figure 7: Dr James Carroll presents on the cost modelling considerations associated with the X-ROTOR project.

Figure 8: Dr Leithead receives honorary EAWE membership (<https://www.wesc2023.eu/photo-gallery>)

The atmosphere was electric with 11 simultaneous sessions occurring in each 2-hour block throughout the day. During the coffee breaks, attendees would get together and discuss what they had learned in their respective sessions. A minor complaint for many people was not being able to sit in on concurrent sessions and engage with every topic in which they were interested. The programme is available on the conference website (wesc2023.eu).

Not only was there a lot of talk about the investigations already conducted, but researchers from UCC were also involved in their own exploration of what attendees thought of the X-ROTOR project. They conducted around 60 surveys and held more in-depth interviews with members of the X-ROTOR team to gain a deeper insight into the range and depth of interesting talents and personalities that constitute this group.

Figure 9: "COVID is over, yeah!!" Social event at WESC, 2023 (<https://www.wesc2023.eu/photo-gallery>)

Of course, it wasn't all work and no play. After a long day of meetings, conference attendees got to enjoy events hosted by Strathclyde during which many of the conversations which began earlier were able to continue into the evening hours.

Academic conference versus industry exhibition. The researchers discovered a few broad differences in the attendees' acceptance of, and interaction with the research project emissaries between this event and the last one in Copenhagen. The WESC attendees welcomed the opportunity to participate in the survey more so than at the industry conference – 35 completed surveys out of 36 engagements versus 27 out of 44 for Wind Europe – but they were less likely to accept the invitation to speak more in depth with the researcher (12 out of 36). There is a practical reason for this reluctance. At WESC, the researchers were limited to speaking with attendees during breaks between sessions. They had limited time before the next session began. At Wind Europe, the target audience were the individuals at the various booths most of whom were representing their company or organization. They were unlikely to be going anywhere for a while. Though WESC provided a greater percentage of completed surveys, the researchers think that the nuanced information provided by the Wind Europe attendees mimics more closely what they would receive from a workshop setting.

Levelized cost of energy LCOE. As was true of the interviews from Wind Europe, the one predominant concern about any new offshore wind turbine design is that it reduces the levelized cost of energy. Of the 12 interviews of attendees, we were able to complete (note: an additional 13 longer format interviews were completed with members of the X-ROTOR team), half of them brought up a lower LCOE as the topmost desired quality in any new turbine concept, one consultant, one parts manufacturer, one wind turbine operator, and three academics. The wind turbine operator from RWE, the largest power producer in the UK (RWE, 2023), said that it was unlikely that an honest LCOE for the X-ROTOR concept would come in lower than that of the traditional HAWTs because it is so non-standard. He said that the LCOE would not come in lower until the concept had reached economies of scale. He said what was more important at this stage was to find a niche market where it would show itself to be profitable and then develop from there.

Reliability. Three of the interviewees who mentioned a lower LCOE – an academic, the consultant, and the parts manufacturer – also mentioned reliability as an important concern. A specific insight from the manufacturer on this issue was the damage that rain could cause for the fast-rotating HAWT blades. He thought that could increase the likelihood of erosion on the component. The academic, concerning reliability, was more interested in a lifecycle assessment of the device.

Wakes. A representative from the US research organisation was particularly interested in the potential of reduced wakes from the X-ROTOR. This point is interesting in that there was a recent revelation from the X-ROTOR team that the design of the device would allow for two of them to be placed much closer together than is possible with traditional HAWTs because they could each be rotating in different directions. As the reader will see after reading section 6 below on attribute matching, highlighting the benefits of lower wakes, or more complementary wakes, is a feature touted by both academics and industry professionals.

Workers. A slightly surprising finding from the interviews is that only one person expressed any concern for how the X-ROTOR would affect its workers in a different way than is experienced with workers on traditional HAWTs. Further, this concern was expressed by a wind energy developer, not one of those politically radical academics. The interviewer suggested that the lower height of the secondary rotors may make the X-ROTOR a safer device for maintenance workers.

Scepticism. Two of the academics interviewed expressed doubt that the X-ROTOR was all it was claimed to be, but they did not offer any specific attribute descriptions with which they disagreed. It may have been that their doubts were not spawned by the design itself but by the description of the indicated attributes in the survey. For example, a name plate rating above 10 MW is important if the aim is to compete with the more powerful offshore wind turbines coming onto the market like Ming Yang's 18+ MW model (Nehls, 2023). If, however, the aim is to design a community sized offshore wind turbine that is cost-effective, it might not need to be more powerful than 5 MW.

Future G2 engagement. Though the conference was informative on many levels, the researchers think that future engagements should focus on trade shows and exhibitions, or other events designed specifically for Industry. The reason for this narrower approach is not that academics are out of touch with industry concerns, their concerns map exceedingly well with those of industry as will be described in section 6. Rather the narrower methodology is intended to satisfy more clearly the Description of Activities' request that G2 engagements follow the workshop approach. Though convening traditional workshops for this group of busy professionals proved logistically problematic, the one-on-one dialogues afforded by trade shows and exhibitions do more closely parallel the nuanced information that one might learn from workshop participants than do the shorter and fewer conversations that can be held during coffee breaks at a lecture-heavy conference.

4.4 Findings from Husum Wind Trade Fair in Husum, Germany

Germany is Europe’s largest producer of wind energy and is the third in the world behind China and the United States (World Population Review, 2024). As such, the wind energy trade fair that takes place in Husum every other year is an essential stop for any industry that wants to do business in this vast and active market. That is why this year there were over 600 exhibitions (compare to the WorldEurope Exhibition in Copenhagen with 500) and more than 15,000 attendees.

Foundation. A few of the interviewees had questions about the foundation type with many thinking that planning the design to be capable of floating-foundation installation was important. They remarked that if it was suitable for floating foundations there would be many more possible deployment sites. Regarding the jacket foundation, one company said that they specialized in casting joints for jacket foundations and could help determine the tension levels that may be exerted on different parts of the jacket structure.

Downtime for repairs. An engineering representative was really impressed by the fact that the turbines could be removed, repaired on shore, and reinstalled all while the turbine was still producing power, albeit at only about 50% - 60% (researcher estimate given that the remaining turbine stays operational). The representative mentioned that fires were the number one reason for downtimes and repairs and wanted to know if we had taken any special measures to prevent this. His company uses drones to monitor wind parks for possible problems.

Figure 10: Unassuming entrance to the fair.

Figure 11: Much more going on inside (5 buildings) (Husum Wind, 2023, p. 3)

Birds. In the ongoing debate in these pages about whether the smaller turbines or louder noises make

Figure 12: Identiflight device for detecting bird species at long distances. It uses Budha Imaging software.

the X-ROTOR safer for birds, the representative from a specialist company could not decide. He said that neither was guaranteed but his company had a solution. Their robot-looking camera device sits out in the offshore park and identifies bird species that are flying toward the devices. The machine identifies if any of the birds are on the endangered list and then it will send a signal to the park's operators of the situation and will recommend which turbines should brake their blades (not necessarily a full-stop, just slow enough for the birds to navigate around them). Of the endangered species flying over German offshore parks (only 2 are specified in the

legislation – the White-Headed Eagle and the Red Kite), only 2.5% slow-down time was required.

Corrosion. As with some responses from the WESC meeting, there was concern about the material or material coatings used as to their ability to prevent corrosion, especially on the lower HAWT blades. A representative from a technical supplier mentioned that her company produced a special coating that protects against salt air, but she was not sure how it would do on the salt air-rain-sea dust corrosion forces on the lower blades and turbines. She wasn't aware of anything on the market for this possible combination of impacts (sea spray and heavy rain on such fast-moving turbine blades so close to the ocean surface).

Loads. A common concern voiced in these interviews was about all the different loads that will be placed on the structure from the ocean waves and currents, the winds, and the rotating structures themselves. A representative from a certification organization, said that this area would occupy much of his investigation. A member of a bolting company wanted to give advice on using a correct tensioner. He said that his company makes a "super bolt" which performs the functions of a regular bolt, but that it is "smart" and can send real-time information to the device operators about the loads being experienced on any part(s) of the structure with the super bolt in use. Use of these devices might be worthwhile in any prototype that is developed.

Appearance. Many interviewees remarked upon the unusual appearance of the X-ROTOR and opined that this quality could hamper uptake of the innovation. A person from a turbine manufacturer had some insights in this regard. The company builds land-based wind turbines that they stand almost three times as high as traditional land-based turbines. In trying to gain public acceptance for these

super tall structures, their research team conducted a public engagement campaign to see which of two different tower designs the public preferred. One design resembled the traditional high-voltage electricity tower. Another one was designed specifically to be more aesthetically pleasing. The second one had an intricate webwork design which was intended to make it less incongruent with the scenery than industrial looking power towers. In a surprise to the researchers, the public preferred the old industrial look to the newer, Eiffel Tower-like design. The reason they most often gave was that it resembled structures that they already saw every day. This representative mentioned that though this observation does not aid in the acceptance of the X-ROTOR, on the bright side, these towers may make it possible for the inventors to consider the X-ROTOR for land-based farms. He opined that if noise is the only reason forcing the X-ROTOR offshore, then maybe the noise impacts will be considerably less for a device whose rotors are 300 meters up in the air rather than at 30. The winds are also more stable and stronger at this height. These new turbine/tower constructs could be placed in existing farms as they will not affect the wake of the current turbines, nor will the current turbines effect their performance.

Lighting. A representative from a lighting system company wondered if the upper blade structure would require aviation warning lights. Because the structure is not as tall as traditional offshore wind turbines, it might not be required to have the lights. Different countries have different laws. The law in Germany is that aviation warning lights are required on any structure more than 100 meters tall. If the X-ROTOR does exceed that height, the rep. said his company's invention could help mitigate the viewscape intrusion. Their lighting system only comes on if there is a plane within 3 miles of the turbine. All other times it is off, and the turbines will not be seen from shore at night.

4.5 Findings from Wind Energy Ireland Trade Show in Dublin, Ireland

From Wednesday, the 11th of October 2023, until Thursday, the 12th, Ireland hosted its first ever wind energy trade show. The event, which took place in Dublin, had over 100 exhibitors and showcased how ready Ireland was for a rapid expansion of her offshore wind energy potential. It attracted visitors from the world over and showed them that it had the supply chain that could make this transition happen. In addition to the hundreds of visitors present at the event, it was attended by some members of the Irish government: Minister Eamon Ryan – Transport, Climate, Environment, &

Figure 14: Main Stage

Figure 13: Minister Simon Convey spotted at the trade show.

Communications and Green Party leader; Minister Dara Calleary – Trade Promotion, Digital and Company Regulation; and Minister Simon Convey – Enterprise, Trade, and Employment and Deputy leader of Fine Gael (Wind Energy Ireland, 2023).

That the event was smaller than the other Group 2 gatherings actually proved an advantage. It was much easier to have longer conversations with the exhibitors and we had easier access to some of the industry's biggest players than at the other events where the wait to talk with someone was often prohibitive.

Noise. The representative for one energy company was really worried about the operational noise on wildlife. That the X-ROTOR is loud is not particularly new information, but we bring it up here again because the company is one of the biggest players in the offshore space and this individual's concern was not the bottom-line, not market share, not even lower LCOE, but animal life. Interesting. He wanted to know how far the noise from the fast-rotating blades would travel in the water. He also figured it would be at a higher pitch which might place it at a disadvantage in this category compared to traditional HAWTs.

Safety. The probability of using rope-work for maintenance tasks was raised again given the lack of a working platform for the workers. He mentioned that the lower blades would have to be able to support two workers, not just one, if for nothing else than just the fact that if there is a rescue situation two people would need to be supported. This person also mentioned that the angle between the top and lower blades needs to be no greater than 120° for the rope work. This representative. from a safety

company also said that including some type of ladder system in the blades consistent with the aerodynamics might be a good idea too.

Foundation. More than one interviewee mentioned that for the best offshore resources in Ireland's territorial waters, we should be designing the X-ROTOR for a floating foundation. These would also be required if we were to explore the ocean between our two dominant Group 1 hosting sites, Islay in Scotland and Malin Head in Ireland.

Gearless direct drive. A representative from a drive company said that though gearless direct drives do have some advantages, it is not as many as once thought. For instance, gearboxes are much more reliable now than they were just a few years ago. She said that the only reason to go gearless is if you are transmitting HVDC and the only reason to do that is if you are more than 80 km from a shore-based substation.⁹ The recent advances in gearbox reliability may be the reason that this attribute figured so unexpectedly low on the attribute matching exercise detailed in the next section.

Artificial reefs. There seems to be an ongoing debate among interviewees about whether creating artificial reefs on the foundations of the turbines is a good idea or not. The general consensus is that the idea needs to be studied further. On the one hand, if the reefs could help increase the fish populations in certain areas, fishermen may be more accepting of the turbines. However, an artificial reef is not necessarily like the *Field of Dreams*¹⁰ – just because it is built does not mean they will come; fish, that is, not the ghosts of baseball players from many years past. There may be more to it than that. Additionally, scoring the foundations for reef creation could lead to growths on all parts of the structure which could weaken it from an engineering perspective. One company said they could monitor things beneath the waterline with their ROV cameras and another said their product not only prevents scouring but could also contribute to reef formation.

Fishing. An interviewee representing the fisheries said OWP developers need to work in concert with the fisheries for the benefit of the local communities involved. The fisheries are not against OWP and realize that their industry is declining while that of OWP is improving, however, it does not have to be a zero-sum game. The ocean is big enough for both to share for the benefit of local economies.

⁹ Information on distance verified at (European Subsea Cables Association, 2023).

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Field_of_Dreams

Nameplate rating. An energy economist at the trade show had some interesting comments about the power rating of the devices. She said that the fact that these turbines are not pursuing the ever-growing chase for double-digit power capacity could work to its advantage in the marketplace. From a risk assessment point of view, if two X-ROTOR devices (5 MW each) could occupy the same space as one 10 MW HAWT, the greater cost could be offset by the reduced risk of extended downtime due

Figure 15: Surprise visitor to the Husum Trade Show

to the X-ROTOR's multiple turbines. Even if one went down, there would still be three more producing power whereas with the traditional HAWT it is all or nothing. The same person said that the design simplicity of the component parts of the X-ROTOR might lend itself more easily to mass production. If X-ROTORS could be turned out on an assembly line they could gain an advantage over the much larger, harder to mass produce, HAWTs.

5 Attribute Matching Revisited

In Deliverable 7.6, we conducted an attribute matching exercise. We surveyed industry representatives and asked what kind of features they would like to see in any new offshore wind turbine design. Determining the preferences for a new offshore wind turbine from experts in the field was a relatively straight forward process. The point of the survey for Group 2 participants was for them to go through a multi-step, iterative process (Delphi Cycle) that would lead to a hierarchical list of criteria, more or less consensus derived, upon which to evaluate the usefulness of the X-ROTOR design for their portfolio of options in building out their assets.

In order to determine what characteristics of the X-ROTOR concept matched these industry experts' opinions, we conducted a thematic analysis of an article by the lead initiator of the X-ROTOR concept, William Leithead, and his group of engineers at University of Strathclyde, Scotland. This peer reviewed article, *The X-ROTOR Offshore Wind Turbine Concept*(2019), presents the most thorough and detailed accounting of the proposed design advantages of this concept.

Since we conducted this first analysis, we have conducted spot interviews with 122 more representatives of companies and organizations which operate in and around the offshore wind power industry and 91 of them completed our survey (75%). After the first iteration of the attribute matching

exercise, we moved beyond the thematic analysis component of the comparison. From the results of this initial exercise, it is clear that the designers of the X-ROTOR concept were in tune with industry needs and designed it accordingly. For our inquiries after this point we changed the survey to show more detail in the decision-making process. A lower LCOE was one of the top ambitions for the authors of this project and it is also the number one concern of industry as expressed in D7.6.

To unpack this concept a little, we decided to omit a lower LCOE as one of the attribute options and instead decided to include some of the different considerations which go into determining the LCOE (e.g., material, installation, O&M, power production, etc.) to see if there was a coalescence around which aspects of the LCOE were most important to consider in this design phase. Seeing that the concept authors and industry experts were on the same page (see how well their considerations of what is important match-up in the table in Appendix 3), we now could turn to just ranking what industry representatives think are the most important attributes of the X-ROTOR according to the new, more detailed questionnaire. The results are in the table below. This list will help promoters of the X-ROTOR showcase the advantages of the design by referencing industry specific preferences for any new offshore wind turbine and then showing how X-ROTOR meets or exceeds these preferences.

Figure 16: 21 attributes of the X-ROTOR design ranked according to importance by industry participants (Group 2)¹¹

	Average of weighted scores	Rank
Description of attribute		
Lower maintenance requirements/increased ease	102.75	1
Survivability	94.25	2
Reduced installation cost	87.25	3
Lower material cost	82	4
Reduced wind turbine wakes	69.5	5
Does not require jack-up boat	68	6
Capacity factor above 60%	66	7
Capable of placement in waters 60 m – 1,000 m deep	65	8
Local job creation	63.5	9
Reduced impact on marine life	61.25	10
Designed to reduce bird collisions	59.5	11
Nameplate rating above 10 MW	58.75	12
Community acceptability	55	13
Single day installation	54.5	14
Placement that reduces conflicts with shipping and fishing activities	53.5	15
Possibility of government subsidies/ FiT/RESS	53.25	16
Possibility of quay-side construction and staging	47.75	17
Noise output	46.25	18
Foundations capable of artificial reef creation	41.5	19
Limited view-scape intrusion	41.25	20
Gearless direct drive	37.5	21

¹¹ The X-ROTOR is not a 10 MW machine, it is closer to 5 MW. The listed attribute (ranked 12th) is meant to reveal whether a high capacity, single unit machine was more important than more units of a smaller power rating.

6 Conclusion

This report detailed the engagement activities and results of our interactions with Group 1 & 2 participants regarding their impressions and concerns for the X-ROTOR concept. An important element of the X-ROTOR project was the capture of stakeholder perspectives to feed into the design and development process. This was realized through engagement with two key stakeholder groups, namely: prospective host communities whose work and lives would be directly affected by potential deployment of such technologies; and the wider wind energy community who have a professional interest in the development of novel turbine designs such as the X-ROTOR concept.

The first group, the prospective host communities (societal stakeholders), were engaged to better understand their practices, attitudes, and values of relevance to the novel wind turbine design, and to examine how – from their perspective – the X-ROTOR design compares with conventional turbine designs.

The second group, the wider wind energy community (industry stakeholders) were engaged to ascertain their opinions and preferences on design (and related) issues including: turbine rating, siting, support structure (fixed/floating), shore-side facilities, installation requirements and operations and maintenance (O&M) practices.

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Appendix 1 – Focus Group Guide

Focus Group Guide

Focus Group Notes

- Participants should be assured of the confidentiality of the project.
- Informed consent should be obtained from all participants.
- The focus group should be recorded, where participants give permission, otherwise detailed notes should be taken.
- Participants should be assured there are no right answers, in all cases we are looking for their experiences and/or their personal opinions.
- Discussion themes are provided as a guide for conversation. An effort should be made to maintain the natural flow of the conversation.

Introduction

This guide has been developed to assist in the planning and delivery of focus groups for the X-ROTOR project. It is based on similar guides produced for other projects within CPPU, and it has been informed by the Focus Group Toolkit developed by CCCSE in The University of Texas at Austin¹² and the Focus Group Guidelines developed by the SWITCH project¹³. A focus group is a small group led through an open discussion by a skilled moderator. The group needs to be large enough to generate rich discussion but not so large that some participants are left out. Focus groups are a method to be used to explore stakeholder perspectives on wind turbine design within the X-ROTOR project.

Key Roles

Moderator

The role of the focus group moderator (or facilitator) is to nurture discussion in an open and spontaneous format. The moderator aims to generate a maximum number of different contributions from as many different people in the available time. The moderator guides the discussion around specific, pre-determined subjects, in an objective, respectful manner. During the focus group, the moderator will

- Follow the discussion outline and activities, as designed, in a consistent manner from group to group; use the same key questions in each session.
- Use a neutral, yet comfortable and inviting tone of voice and facial expressions.

¹² Focus Group Tool Kit, Center for Community College Student Engagement, The University of Texas at Austin
<http://www.ccsse.org/focusgrouptoolkit/>

¹³ Focus Group Guidelines, SWITCH Intelligent Energy Europe project
https://www.polisnetwork.eu/uploads/Modules/PublicDocuments/switch_focus-group-guidelines.pdf

- Ask questions to clarify participants' points and increase understanding of each point made by participants.
- Ensure that each participant contributes throughout the conversation.
- Remind participants of the value of differing points of view.
- Be respectful of all points of view and instruct those in the group to do the same.
- Keep the discussion moving to stay within the specified time frame.

Assistant and Note-taker

The moderator is supported by an assistant and note-taker. The assistant takes notes and oversees the audio-recording. The objective of the note taking is to accurately pull the principal points from the discussion while it is not meant as a transcript nor should it be an interpretation of the participants' contributions. Accordingly, audio recording is preferred because it allows for accurate capture of the original conversation – notes are used to clarify data that is unclear on the recordings.

Recruiting / Selecting participants

Participants will be recruited such that they comprise a diverse profile, in terms of gender, and energy experiences. Focus group participants will be recruited by the research team directly or via partners' networks. All participants should be over 18 years of age. The focus groups should take place locally in the case study locations or as otherwise convenient for the participants. The engagements should be designed and realized in such a manner to promote gender, economic, and physical inclusivity – including *e.g.*, timing, location, format, supports, *etc.*

Overview of Focus Group Session

Preliminary

1. As participants enter, participants will be asked to sign in.
2. The facilitator will introduce themselves and the note taker.
3. The purpose of focus group will be explained and the facilitator will go through the briefing document, answering any queries and ensuring that all participants are clear on its content.
4. The reason for audio-recording will be explained and the anonymity of the participants' contributions will be reiterated.
5. Participants will be invited to give their consent by signing the consent forms – they will again be reminded that they are free to stop participating at any point

Arrangements

6. The facilitator will explain their primary role, which is to ask questions, stimulate a discussion, and to keep the discussion on track.
7. Participants' will be informed that their role is to share their experiences, attitudes, opinions and feelings. The facilitator will emphasise that there are no right or wrong answers, and encourage all participants to contribute fully to the discussion.

8. The logistics of the focus group will be outlined. *i.e.*, 90 minutes discussion, mobile phones on silent, bathroom breaks as required, refreshments provided, *etc.*
9. The focus group ground rules will be outlined, and participants will be asked to agree that: one person speaks at a time; no side conversations; no one is allowed to dominate; everyone is given a chance to be heard; there are no right or wrong answers; the discussion is about experiences; they will respect the confidentiality of discussions.

Focus Group Discussion

While the objective is a free-flowing discussion where participants are allowed to say what is important to them, there are of course intended outcomes. The questions below show the questions which will structure the engagement and direct the discussion towards meeting the planned objectives.

Introductions

Participants introduce themselves and outline what they expect from the focus group

Outcome 1: to understand context of participants' contributions

- 1) What does the sea mean to you? Why?
- 2) How do you feel about Climate change?
Do you believe climate change is occurring? What do you think has caused it?

Outcome 2: to capture perspectives on off-shore wind

- 3) Participants will form break-out groups to consider the following statements before reconvening for a plenary discussion
 - Offshore wind farms are good
 - Offshore wind turbines are a serious problem for fishing
 - Offshore wind turbines damage leisure and tourism
 - Wildlife is disturbed by offshore wind turbines
 - Offshore wind can create jobs for people living along the coast
 - Offshore wind turbines are a problem as they kill seabirds
 - Offshore wind can generate electricity cheaply
 - Offshore wind turbines are noisy

Outcome 3: to gather feedback on the turbine design

Participants are provided information and shown details, including mock-ups, of the new turbine design and invited to provide feedback through open ended questions ...

How does this design compare with conventional turbines?

- a. What do you like about the new design compared to older turbines? Why?
- b. Are there elements of the new design do you not like? Why?
- 4) If there was one thing about the new design you would change, what would it be?
- 5) Would this new design change your feelings towards offshore wind? In what way?

Summary and close

6) Have you any final thoughts?

Facilitator will ask participants if they have any final questions or comments – following which the facilitator will thank them for their participation once more.

Appendix 2: Companies engaged at trade fairs

Copenhagen		Husum	
Bax Energy	Kingspor	Jaechong	Beventum
Tractabel	FT Technologies	Umspannwerke	Fukushima Recycling
Subsea Services	4C Offshore	Synflex	Winenergy
Foresight Magazine	Dansk Polyglass	Belfor	Nord-Lac
Wind Power Monthly	Barge Master	Leymann	Anecto
Actu Marine	Atos	Budha Imaging	Lanthan Safe Sky
Acciona	OX2	Argo Hytas	GE WI
Storm Geo	Shoreline	Tunvard	
SSF Renewables	Kent		1 researcher, 1.25 days
Invenergy	Nvisionist		
Ostr Wind	New Citizen Design		
DT Bird and Bat	VUB		
Normec	Leeds		
DNV	Kodiak		
Endiprev	Mott McDonald	RWE	TCI group
Maple Power	Corrosion	ASC Safety and Training	KER
Deutsche Wind Guard	CbIME	Nordex	Margaret Callinane
DHSS	Maelig	Geosynrthesis	LP3
Siemens	Larko	Kellybegs Marine Clust	Mega AWE
HAWE		ABO	HBMV
	2 researchers, 2 days	WEI	Farra Marine
		blauwe cluster	Arneoceancrestmarine
		D.P Energy	Dos Santos
		Film-Ocean	2nd one from Film Ocean
		GE-Sales	Star Fared Health
Academic Conference, all responses (34) anonymous		Rockbags	Bordeaux Corp
	3 researchers, 2 days	Rescordan ROVs	Shemes Energy Initiative
	And interviews of	Gurt Ireland	
	X-ROTOR Team		3 researchers, 1 day

Appendix 3: Attribute matching table from D 7.6

Attribute Matching Table

Survey Rank	Survey Category from Yr1, G2 expert survey of what they feel is most important in a new OW turbine design	Attributes derived from a thematic analysis of (Leithead <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Occurrences after 2 nd iteration, ranked
1	LCOE	Survivability	15
2	Survivability	Secondary rotors	14
3	Installation costs	Reduced LCOE	10
4	Maintenance costs	O&M costs	9
5	Purchase costs	Turbine costs	8
6	O&M costs	Direct drive, no gearbox	5
7	Choice of power capacity	Floating platform poss.	3
8	Effect on people	Up-scalability	3
9	Effect on wildlife	Power capacity	2
10	Onshore requirements	Reduced primary rotor size	
11	Height	Noise	1
12	Bird collisions	Local jobs	1
13	Impact on fishing		
14	Fixed or floating	Not mentioned in article	
15	Effect on radio/radar		

– Visibility, impact on shipping, noise output, and impacts on scenery were left off the survey response column because they fell within the fifth quintile, i.e., they were not in the top 80% of responses from industry experts regarding characteristics that they thought were most important for a new turbine design.